

Differentiating between structural and functional spinal deformities in children and adolescents using machine learning

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Abstract: Severe skeletal disorders of children are often mistaken for poor posture, leading to late admittance to treatment and thus limiting treatment outcome and patients' quality of life. This work proposes a machine learning based methodology to differentiate between structural and functional spinal deformities. Four machine learning algorithms combined with feature engineering were used to train a dataset of 262 rasterstereographic measurements, containing the classes "scoliosis", "other structural deformities" and "functional deformities". The overall achieved F1-score was 0.876 with support vector machine. Based on these results, we propose rasterstereography as a novel method for determining the type of spinal deformities.

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I. Introduction

Since structural and functional spinal deformities in childhood often appear alike [1,2] they can prove challenging to distinguish. This leads to late admittance to necessary treatment [1,3]; however, time is a crucial aspect when it comes to treating skeletal disorders in children [4]. Once admitted to further diagnostics, functional tests may provide insight into the underlying condition [2] and, when structural causes are suspected, these are supplemented by imaging, such as ionizing chest radiographs [1,4]. Multiple steps are required until a diagnosis can be reached.

Human posture is the result of complex interplay of morphologic-static (e.g., bone structures) and functional-dynamic (e.g., muscles, tendons) aspects, continuously influencing each other to shape an individual's posture [5]. Functional spinal deformities are classified into lordotic posture, kyphotic posture, flat-back posture and sway-back posture, while structural spinal deformities reflect clinical conditions such as adolescent idiopathic scoliosis (AIS) or juvenile kyphosis [2].

This study proposes a supervised machine learning (ML) approach for detecting and differentiating structural and functional deformities with video rasterstereography (VRS). This non-invasive measuring system projects lines of light on a patient's back and analyzes the curvatures to approximate the shape of the spine. This study further explores to what extent it is possible to detect structural deformities with VRS and which feature combinations are used most effectively by different ML algorithms for this task.

II. Material and methods

Our study included 155 patients admitted to the pediatric department of the provincial hospital in Kielce, Poland (70 male, 85 female, aged 7 to 19 years). Including follow-ups, we recorded a total of 262 rasterstereographic measurements (DIERS formetric 4D, DIERS International GmbH, Schlangenbad, Germany), each labeled with the patient's diagnosed condition: 208 AIS, 16 with other structural spinal deformities (OSD) (e.g., ICD-10 M40 and M43) and 38 with functional spinal deformities (FD). The methodology is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: It is the aim to identify whether a structural or functional condition is the cause of a spinal deformity. Since VRS provides 132 anatomical features, analyzing and reducing the feature space is crucial for achieving this goal.

The software DICAM 3 (DIERS International GmbH) was used to calculate 132 features, characterizing the anatomy of the shoulders, spine and pelvis in all three body planes. To improve the decision-making process, average, rms, maximum, minimum and sum values of rotational, flexional and extensional data of all vertebrae were calculated. This created 15 combined vertebrae features that may enhance the information gain. To study the effect of these and to avoid cross-influencing, models were trained in different feature spaces, including and excluding the single vertebrae values.

Four machine learning algorithms were trained on the data, applying group 10-fold cross-validation: k-nearest neighbor (kNN) with $k=10$, Naive Bayes (NB), Decision Tree (DT) and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The wrapper methods sequential forward floating selection (SFFS) and sequential backward floating selection (SBFS) were applied to reduce feature complexity. Weighted F1 metric, sensitivity (SEN) and specificity (SPC) were calculated to evaluate the results.

III. Results and discussion

The ML algorithms achieved the highest performance when analyzing between 8 to 47 features, depending on the algorithm, with the F1 score reaching 0.860 (DT), 0.858 (SVM), 0.823 (kNN) and 0.797 (NB). The best feature space reflects a selection of objective anatomical parameters, such as trunk inclination, lateral deviation and pelvic torsion. Combined vertebrae features, especially “average vertebrae rotation”, were selected by all algorithms and increased the F1 score up to 0.876 (SVM) (Fig. 2) and 0.872 (DT). The sensitivity for AIS, OSD and FD was 0.95, 0.37 and 0.71 respectively (see Table 1).

Figure 2: Full feature space iteration, including combined vertebrae features. The best performing algorithm for this combination was SVM followed by DT. DT performed equally high in a feature space that excluded single vertebrae features.

The results reflect a good classification rate of AIS and FD, however, there is a bias towards the largest group AIS. The class containing OSD had a poor classification rate, a possible reason being that it only consisted of 16 measurements but contained the broadest patient set. To improve the classification rate, it would be necessary to increase the number of subjects with ICD-10 diagnoses M40 and M43, perhaps splitting the group if the cohort size permits.

Regarding the combined vertebrae features, only the rotational values had an impact and improved the results compared to when only single value vertebrae features were used. This may either suggest a high importance of rotational values for differentiating functional from structural deformities or, since AIS was the majority class, a high relevance for identifying AIS.

Table 1: Sensitivity and specificity for (a) SVM (47 features) and (b) DT (16 features). The class OSD reached a higher sensitivity when trained with DT.

Class	SEN-a	SPC-a	SEN-b	SPC-b
AIS	0.95	0.67	0.95	0.74
OSD	0.37	0.98	0.50	0.97
FD	0.71	0.96	0.63	0.95

There are some limitations to this study. Due to the limited sample size no test set was created to verify the cross-validation results. The algorithms, however, can be tested once further data is acquired. The dataset was unbalanced, containing a large class of AIS. Since AIS patients often develop a flatback [4] and FD in this dataset contained about 50 % patients with round back, further investigations should examine this influence on the results. More clinical data is needed to balance the dataset and thus expand the scope of this study with a broader variety of structural spinal conditions.

IV. Conclusions

With a classification rate of $F1 = 0.87$, this study suggests that VRS has great potential for an automated differentiation between structural and functional spinal deformities. DT and SVM achieved similar results, while DT did so with a smaller feature space (16 features). Overall, this method is very promising to pave the way for time-efficient diagnoses and much-needed screening tools.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

Research funding: This work is part of the M-ERA.Net project MBrace (grant number: F-012739-751-0E0-1120701) and is co-financed with tax funds on the basis of the budget passed by the Saxon State Parliament. Conflict of interest: Authors state no conflict of interest. Informed consent: Informed consent has been obtained from all individuals included in this study. Ethical approval: The research related to human use complies with all the relevant national regulations, institutional policies and was performed in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration, and has been approved by the Ethics Committee of Jan Kochanowski University Kielce (protocol code: No. 26/2022, date of approval: 01 April 2022).

REFERENCES

- [1] Ali RM, Green DW, Patel TC, *Scheuermann's kyphosis*, Curr Opin Pediatr. 1999 Feb;11(1):70-5. doi: 10.1097/00008480-199902000-00014. PMID: 10084088.
- [2] Czaprowski D, *Non-structural misalignments of body posture in the sagittal plane*, Scoliosis Spinal Disord. 2018 Mar 5;13:6. doi: 10.1186/s13013-018-0151-5. PMID: 29516039; PMCID: PMC5836359.
- [3] Thomas G. Lowe, *Scheuermann's Kyphosis*, in Neurosurgery Clinics of North America, Volume 18, Issue 2, 2007, Pages 305-315, ISSN 1042-3680, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nec.2007.02.011>.
- [4] Negrini S, Donzelli S, Aulisa AG, Czaprowski D, Schreiber S, de Mauroy JC, et al, *2016 SOSORT guidelines: orthopaedic and rehabilitation treatment of idiopathic scoliosis during growth in Scoliosis and Spinal Disorders*. 13: 3. doi:10.1186/s13013-017-0145-8.
- [5] F. J. Wagenhäuser, *Die Klinik der Haltungstörungen und des Morbus Scheuermann*, in Zeitschrift für Präventivmedizin 14.1 (1969), S. 157–170. DOI: 10.1007/BF02036138.